

On the compression of mineral barite, BaSO₄. A structural study.

D. Santamaría-Pérez^{a,*},† and R. Chuliá-Jordán^a

^a *Departamento de Química-Física I, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Avda. Complutense s/n, 28040, Madrid, Spain.*

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to contribute to a better understanding of the behaviour of mineral barite, BaSO₄, at high pressures, particularly the recently reported phase transition at 27 GPa to a new structure type. For this purpose, we will focus on the evolution of its BaS cation array with pressure, which will additionally allow for a rational description of the structure. When the initial *Pnma* barite structure transforms into the also orthorhombic *P2₁2₁2₁* structure, no change in the coordination number of Ba or S atoms occurs ([SO₄] tetrahedra and [BaO₁₂] dodecahedra). However, the second coordination sphere presents an increase of neighbour atoms and a decrease of the Ba – S distances. This rearrangement of atoms is related to the Buerger's mechanism of the B1 – B2 phase transition for the BaS cation array, confirming that cations (second neighbours) do not arrange in an arbitrary way.

* Corresponding author: dsantamaria@quim.ucm.es

† MALTA Consolider Team

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1 - Introduction

Mineral barite, BaSO₄, crystallizes at ambient conditions in an orthorhombic structure (space group: *Pnma*, No. 62, *Z* = 4) [1] which is usually very poorly described in crystallochemistry books as formed by cation-centered (Ba and S) oxygen polyhedra. Thus, according to this descriptive model, this sulphate would be only formed by isolated [SO₄] tetrahedra and complex [BaO₁₂] dodecahedra (see Fig. 1a). More recently, Vegas

[2] described the structure of BaSO₄ in terms of its cation subarray BaS which is of the FeB-type (B27), the structure consisting of triangular prisms of Ba atoms that share faces along the *b* direction and corners in the other two directions, with the [SO₄] groups inserted into these metal prisms (see Fig. 1b). This approach allows for a more rational description of the structure of this mineral.

BaSO₄ compound has recently been of renewed interest regarding its high-pressure (HP) behaviour [3-6]. After some controversy on the existence of a HP phase, Santamaría-Pérez *et al.* [6] found that compression induces a phase transition at 27 GPa from the barite *Pnma* structure to another orthorhombic structure, *P2₁2₁2₁* (No. 19, *Z* = 4), which the authors claim to be a significant distortion of the initial phase. This lattice transformation entails a small displacement and tilting movement of the [SO₄] tetrahedra, but no change in the coordination number of the Ba atoms occurs.

In this paper, we will try to better understand the transition mechanism of this pressure-induced phase transition by analyzing the displacements of the second neighbour atoms, i.e. the evolution of the structure of the BaS cation subarray. In the FeB-type structure of the BaS array in barite, each atom is surrounded by 7 atoms, reason why it can be considered as intermediate structure between the NaCl-type (B1, C.N.= 6) and the CsCl-type (B2, C.N.= 8). This study shows that the rearrangement of atoms at the phase transition is related to the Buerger's mechanism of the B1 – B2 phase transition [7, 8] for the BaS cation subarray, confirming that cations (second neighbours) would suffer a sequence of structural transformations along the path: NaCl-type → FeB-type → *P2₁2₁2₁*-type → CsCl-type.

2 - Discussion

Structural coincidences between element and alloys, on one hand, and the cation subarray in different oxides, on the other, have been reported by several groups [9-11]. However, these coincidences are no such and the fact that cations try to reproduce the structure of the corresponding elements and alloys in spite of being embedded in an oxygen matrix was later confirmed [2, 12-18]. This led Vegas and coworkers to establish the concept of “real stuffed alloy” for those oxides whose cation arrays maintain the structure of the corresponding alloy [12]. This concept would allow us to better explain the structural changes observed in BaSO₄ under strong compression.

The cation subarray BaS in barite at ambient conditions adopts the FeB-type structure, which is a mere distortion of the atomic arrangement in the cubic NaCl-type structure. This can be easily seen by comparing Fig. 2a and 2b. The lattice parameters and atomic positions of the ambient conditions barite structure are collected in Table I. Six distances Ba – S would define the distorted NaCl-type net ($1 \times 3.51 \text{ \AA}$, $2 \times 3.55 \text{ \AA}$, $2 \times 3.66 \text{ \AA}$ and $1 \times 3.96 \text{ \AA}$) and an additional distance of 4.19 \AA would complete the coordination sphere of 7 neighbours (second coordination sphere if the O atoms are considered). Thus, the structure of barite may be regarded as a BaS array of the FeB-type with the three oxygen atoms inserted in $[\text{SBA}_3]$ tetrahedra and one O atom located approximately along one Ba – S contact (distance of 4.19 \AA).

It is important to note that, at high temperature, BaSO_4 transforms into a cubic $F\text{-}43m$ phase where the Ba and S atoms adopt NaCl-type structure, with six atoms in the coordination sphere [19] (see Fig. 2a). The same configuration is adopted in the corresponding sulfide at room conditions [20] and, therefore, it can be considered as an example of structural identity between the cation subarray in the oxide and its corresponding alloy (in this case, barium sulfide BaS) [2, 9].

In this respect, it is interesting to evaluate how the binary sulfide behaves under pressure. Weir *et al.* [21] carried out energy-dispersive x-ray diffraction experiments on BaS and found the rocksalt (B1) phase to be stable up to 6.5 GPa. At this pressure, the sample undergoes a structural phase transition to the B2 phase, which remains up to 89 GPa, the highest pressure reached in the study. Hence, the CsCl-type structure is a structural candidate for the cation subarray of BaSO_4 at high pressure.

The room-conditions FeB-type structure of the BaS subarray is also consistent with the idea of equivalence between oxidation and pressure, which establishes an analogy between the insertion of oxygen and the application of pressure [17]. In this way, the BaS subarray in barite would stabilize a structure which could correspond to that of a possible high-pressure phase of the sulphide; i.e. the FeB-type structure could be a metastable phase of BaS at high pressures, a plausible intermediate in the NaCl- \rightarrow CsCl-type structural sequence.

High-pressure x-ray diffraction measurements on BaSO_4 performed by Santamaría-Pérez *et al.* [6] have shown that compression induces a phase transition at 27 GPa from the barite $Pnma$ structure to another orthorhombic structure, $P2_12_12_1$ (see Fig. 3). The unit cell dimensions and the fractional coordinates of this structure at 40.5 GPa are

collected in Table II. This HP structure implies a volume change of about 2% at the transition: the a axis contracts approximately 18.3%, the b axis expands 20% and the c axis remains nearly constant. This lattice transformation entails a significant tilting movement of the $[\text{SO}_4]$ tetrahedra (see Fig. 3). As mentioned above, no change in the coordination number of either the S or the Ba atoms occurred. The BaS framework, however, changes considerably as shown in Fig. 2c (to be compared to Fig. 2a and 2b). It still resembles to a rocksalt structure which would have been elongated along the direction $[110]$ (which corresponds to the direction of the b axis of the $P2_12_12_1$ unit cell). The distorted $[\text{Ba}_4\text{S}_4]$ “cubes”, with torsion angles that range from 0 to 20 degrees, now present angles $\angle \text{A-A-A}$ of approx. 60° and 120° in the (110) plane. Due to this distortion, the coordination number of both the S and Ba atoms in the cation subarray increases to eight, as in the B2 structure. The Ba – S distances range from 3.11 to 3.94 Å (1×3.11 Å, 1×3.12 Å, 1×3.22 Å, 1×3.33 Å, 1×3.5 Å, 1×3.81 Å, 1×3.9 Å, 1×3.94 Å). It is important to highlight that, even if the coordination number coincides with that of the CsCl-type structure, the geometry of its coordination sphere still differs. This can be seen in Fig. 4, where the evolution of the coordination sphere in the structural sequence NaCl-type \rightarrow FeB-type \rightarrow $P2_12_12_1$ -type \rightarrow CsCl-type is depicted. The arrangement of the Ba atoms surrounding a S atom is not far away from that of the B2 structure, seven of these Ba atoms adopting a quasi-cube configuration. Only the eighth Ba atom should change its position in order to attain the coordination sphere of the CsCl-type structure.

The oxygen atoms of the HP-BaSO₄ phase are rearranged in such a way that an increasing in the second sphere coordination number is allowed. A very interesting point is that the position of the anions can give a precise idea of where the electron density would be located in the binary BaS compound with this structural type, as reported elsewhere [22]. It must be also mentioned that some authors have considered that the position of the oxygen atoms could be the key parameter for eventual structural changes in oxides as pressure is increased [23]. According to this, changes of structures consisting of different oxygen polyhedra could be described by the deformation of the sphere packing which is built up by oxygen anions [23]. This approach seems not to be easily applied in the case of barium sulphate.

Regarding the preceding, the transition path NaCl-type \rightarrow FeB-type \rightarrow $P2_12_12_1$ -type \rightarrow CsCl-type is a plausible mechanism for the transformation of the B1 into the B2

structure in AX compounds under compression. This mechanism is related to that suggested by Buerger [7, 8], in which the B1 – B2 transformation is viewed as the opening of the rhombohedral angles of the primitive B1 cell (from 60 to 90°) coupled to simultaneous change in the lattice spacing. However, our results suggest that the $P2_12_12_1$ structure observed in the cation subarray of BaSO₄ could be an intermediate framework for this phase transition. In it, the structure would not be compressed along the diagonal of the cubic cell but along the diagonal of one of the unit cell faces. This pressure-induced structural sequence also suggests that barite, BaSO₄, could transform into a new structure with the CsCl-type BaS cation subarray at very high pressures.

3 - Conclusions

The high-pressure phase transition of BaSO₄ has been studied by means of a systematic analysis of the structural changes suffered by its BaS cation subarray. This is supported by the well-established fact that cations in oxides tend to reproduce the structure of the corresponding elements and alloys in spite of being embedded in an oxygen matrix [2, 12-18]. Barite seems to behave in a similar way as shown by the structural identity between barium sulfide at room conditions and the cation subarray of the high-temperature phase of its corresponding sulfate BaSO₄. This study suggests that the phase transition in barite is somehow determined by the pressure-induced transformations B1 to B2 in the cation network, BaS, following the stepwise structural sequence NaCl-type → FeB-type → $P2_12_12_1$ -type → CsCl-type. Thus, the evolution of the second-neighbour coordination sphere is crucial to understand this particular phase transition. What's more, cations in oxides seem to arrange in a non-arbitrary way and, even if surprising, they determine the whole tridimensional structure.

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Table I.- Fractional coordinates corresponding to the room-conditions phase of BaSO₄. The structure is orthorhombic (S.G. *Pnma*) with lattice parameters $a = 8.8721(4)$ Å, $b = 5.4522(2)$ Å and $c = 7.1491(3)$ Å.

Atoms	Sites	x	y	z
Ba	4c	0.6845(2)	0.25	0.3418(2)
S	4c	0.5624(7)	0.25	0.8097(8)
O1	4c	0.411(2)	0.25	0.890(2)
O2	4c	0.681(2)	0.25	0.953(2)
O3	8d	0.4201(9)	0.9714(13)	0.3149(13)

Table II.- Fractional coordinates corresponding to the high-pressure phase of BaSO₄ at 40.5 GPa. The structure is orthorhombic (S.G. *P2₁2₁2₁*) with lattice parameters $a = 6.55(5)$ Å, $b = 5.87(4)$ Å and $c = 6.33(4)$ Å.

Atoms	Sites	x	y	z
Ba	4a	0.632(1)	0.294(1)	0.576(1)
S	4a	0.634(2)	0.239(3)	0.080(2)
O1	4a	0.472(2)	0.144(4)	0.205(3)
O2	4a	0.838(5)	0.285(3)	0.201(5)
O3	4a	0.439(7)	0.927(6)	0.515(4)
O4	4a	0.697(3)	0.054(2)	0.921(4)

Figure captions

Figure 1.- (a) Structure of barite at room conditions projected on to the *ac*-plane according to the description in terms of isolated [SO₄] tetrahedra and complex [BaO₁₂] polyhedra. Light grey, medium grey and tiny dark grey circles represent Ba, S and O atoms, respectively. (b) Structure of BaSO₄ in terms of its cation subarray BaS². It is formed by trigonal prisms of Ba in which the [SO₄] units are inserted. The skeleton of the BaS cation subarray is similar to the structure of the alloy FeB.

Figure 2.- (a) Unit-cell of the B1 structure of the sulphide BaS at room conditions. The cation subarray of the high-temperature phase of BaSO₄ also adopts this structure. (b) BaS cation subarray of barite at room conditions, which is a strong distortion of the NaCl-type structure. (c) BaS cation subarray of the high-pressure phase of BaSO₄. Its framework still resembles that of the rocksalt structure but considerably compressed along the diagonal of the (00n) planes of the original NaCl-type structure. Unit-cell edges, Ba – S contacts that would correspond to the NaCl-type structure and additional contacts are represented as black solid, medium-gray solid and light-gray dashed lines, respectively.

Figure 3.- Structure of the high-pressure phase of BaSO₄ at 40.5 GPa projected also on to the *ac*-plane⁶. In this structure, the trigonal prisms of Ba in which the [SO₄] units were inserted are highly distorted as a consequence of the tilting of these [SO₄] tetrahedra. To be compared with Fig. 1b. Light grey, medium grey and tiny dark grey circles represent Ba, S and O atoms, respectively.

Figure 4.- Coordination sphere of the S atoms in: (a) the NaCl-type structure of barium sulphide BaS at room conditions → Octahedral coordination, C.N. = 6. (b) The cation subarray BaS of the room conditions structure of BaSO₄ → FeB-type, C.N. = 7. (c) The cation subarray BaS of the high-pressure structure of BaSO₄ → S.G. *P2₁2₁2₁*, C.N. = 8. (d) The CsCl-type structure of barium sulphide BaS at high pressure → cubic coordination, C.N. = 8. The stepwise evolution of the coordination sphere (increase in the coordination number) in the structural sequence NaCl-type → FeB-type → *P2₁2₁2₁*-

type → CsCl-type is obvious. Ba – S bonds or contacts and Ba – Ba contacts are represented as solid dark-gray lines and dashed light-gray lines, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4